

Bioefficacy Test of Different Chemotherapeutic Substances against *Aspergillus* sp. and *Chrysosporium* sp. Contaminants of Tissue-Cultured Abaca (*Musa textiles* NEE.) during Initial Stage of Micropropagation

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between both authors. Author JSC designed the study, performed the statistical analysis, wrote the protocol and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. Author AMF managed the analyses of the study and managed the literature searches. Both authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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ABSTRACT

The study was conducted at the Tissue Culture Laboratory and Crop Research Laboratory of the University of Southeastern Philippines to test the efficacy of selected antibiotics and antifungal agents in the elimination of the common fungi contaminant of tissue-cultured abaca meriplants during initial stage of propagation on the Murashige and Skoog medium.

Microbial symptoms were observed based on their colony shape, colony margin/ elevation and colony color in 20 bottle test media during one month (Initial stage) observation period. The technique of James and Natalie was adopted for identification of the unknown isolated fungi. The species encountered were identified and characterized following the technique of James and Natalie. The Poisoned Food Technique for Antibiotic Sensitivity Testing for Fungi was used. The

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experiment was laid-out in completely randomized design (CRD) with five treatments replicated three times. There were five plates per replicate for a total of 75 plates. The treatments were: T1-Control (No treatment); T2-Streptomycin ($200 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$); T3-Nystatin ($1 \text{ ml}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$); T4-Streptomycin ($200 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) + Nystatin ($1 \text{ ml}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$); and T5-Benomyl (Chemical check, $100 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$).

Study showed that the common contaminants of tissue-cultured abaca were fungal colonies such as *Aspergillus* sp. and *Chrysosporium* sp. like fungus appeared on the 10th day and 12th day after initiation, respectively with a total of 15% rate of occurrence.

Result of *in vitro* test likewise showed that T5 - Benomyl (Chemical check, $100 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) significantly inhibited the growth of *Aspergillus* sp. T3 - Nystatin ($1 \text{ ml}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) also inhibited the growth of fungal contaminants same as *Chrysosporium* sp. These fungal species were found to cause death of the culture biological material by some probable sources of contaminations, such as handling of plant materials, culture vessels and the laboratory. The result of the study suggests that both Benomyl (Chemical check, $100 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) and Nystatin ($1 \text{ ml}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) can be used to inhibit growth of fungal contaminants, such as *Aspergillus* sp. and *Chrysosporium* sp. like fungus.

Keywords: *Abaca; Aspergillus; Chrysosporium; contamination; fungi; Musa textiles; tissue culture.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Philippines is the world's largest producer of abaca fiber, accounting for about 85% share of the global production in 2013 to present. In the Philippines, abaca plants are cultivated across 130 thousand hectares of land by over 90 thousand farmers. Abaca fiber is primarily used as a raw material by end industries, such as pulp and paper, fiber craft, cordage, etc. Abaca fiber consumption in the Philippines is witnessing a continuous increase among this end, user industries due to widening applications of the fiber [1].

Abaca plantlet propagation is now practiced worldwide by cloning through tissue culture. Plant tissue culture refers to growing and multiplication of cell, tissues and organs on defined solid and liquid media under aseptic and controlled environment. The primary advantage of micropropagation or tissue culture is rapid production of high quality, disease-free and uniform planting materials [2].

Even though it is possible to produce a large number of plants by micropopagation, one of the greatest problems in this technique is contamination. A wide range of microorganisms (filamentous fungi, yeast, bacteria, viruses and viroids) and micro-arthropods (mites and thrips) have been identified as contaminants in plant tissue cultures [2]. Contaminants may be introduced with the explant, during manipulation in laboratory or by micro-arthropods vectors [3,4]. Frequently encountered bacterial and fungal contamination in laboratories of commercial micropropagation posed considerable problem [5]. Tissue cultures can become contaminated at

any stage of tissue culturing process [6]. The common fungi contamination of tissue culture abaca is *Aspergillus* sp. and *Chrysosporium* sp. [7].

Several antibiotics are frequently used in plant biotechnology to eliminate endogenous fungal contaminants in plant tissue culture [8,9]. The efficacy of antibiotics can be assessed by their ability to inhibit bacterial or fungal growth [9]. Hence, antibiotic screening remains the primary requisites for tackling the covert contamination problem. This study, was therefore conducted to test the efficacy of selected antibiotics and antifungal agents in the elimination of the common fungi contaminant of tissue-cultured abaca during initial stage of propagation.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study Area

The study was conducted at the Tissue Culture Laboratory and Crop Research Laboratory of the University of Southeastern Philippines, Tagum-Mabini Campus, Mabini Unit, Pindasan, Mabini, Compostela Valley Province from October 2015 to February 2016. The isolation room was maintained in aseptic condition or free from any contamination. The laminar hood was sprayed with 10% zonrox/ethanol. The UV light was turned on for 30 minutes before use of the isolation room.

2.2 Establishment and Stabilization of Explants in Culture

This was done by selecting healthy suckers of abaca for tissue culture. Diseased-free young

suckers (50 cm-100 cm long) of *Musa textiles* Née were collected from the 'Abaca' area of the University of Southeastern Philippines, Mabini, Compostela Valley Province. Each sucker was cut into 1-3 inches quarters. Abaca suckers collected from the field were washed in tap water and air-dried. The upper middle portion and the outer bracts of the suckers were removed with sharp knife and the remaining basal portion was washed with pure solution of 1 liter commercial sodium chloride solution. The next layers of leaves and excess corm tissues were removed to obtain a block measuring 6 to 8 cm long, 3 to 5 cm in diameter and soaked in the same commercial bleach solution for 20 minutes. The media and glass wares were sterilized for 15 minutes using pressure cooker at 15 psi. The modified Murashige and Skoog medium [10] was used and added with five different rates of antibiotics depending on the treatments used and pH was adjusted to 5.9 before sterilization for 15 minutes. For each treatment, 4-5 explants (20 media culture) were used.

Under aseptic condition, inside the laminar flow, superfluous tissues were removed by trimming away the tightly overlapping leaf sheaths and bases, exposing the meristematic cells in between the leaf bases. The shoot tip was decapitated and a block of tissue about 1.5 cm³ was excised, divided into four quarters and inoculated onto the multiplication MS medium with 5 mg/L Benzyl adenine plant growth regulators having four explants per vessel. The cultures were labeled, transferred to the growing culture room and incubated at 26-28°C with 16/8 hours light/dark cycle for four weeks using 15 watts fluorescent lights. During incubation in the growth room, cultures were inspected for contamination and mortality of explant tissues daily for one month.

The disinfected explant was placed in a bottle of solidified nutrient MS agar medium without antibiotic (control). Detectable fungal contaminants were isolated and sub cultured into the fresh Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) medium two to four days after incubation of the explants. Fungi culture disks were transferred to fresh culture medium and incubated at 30-32°C for three to five days. Detected fungal contaminants with highest frequency of occurrence were inoculated into PDA medium. The isolates were purified by series of transfers to fresh PDA culture medium. Identification using the technique of James and Natalie [10] of fungal contaminants was done 4-7 days after

transferring into fresh medium when pure cultures were obtained.

2.3 Antibiotic Sensitivity Testing for Fungi: Poisoned Food Technique

The experiment was laid-out in completely randomized design (CRD) with five treatments replicated three times. There were five plates per replicate for a total of 75 plates. The treatments were: T1-Control (No treatment); T2-Streptomycin (200 mg·L⁻¹); T3-Nystatin (1 ml·L⁻¹); T4-Streptomycin (200 mg·L⁻¹) + Nystatin (1 ml·L⁻¹); and T5-Benomyl (Chemical check, 100 mg·L⁻¹).

The potato tubers were washed, diced (250 g), placed in casserole and simmered in 500 ml distilled water for 15-20 minutes or until soft. The potato broth was decanted through gauze cloth into beaker and set aside. Previously soaked shredded agar (20 g) and dextrose powder (20 g) were melted in 500 ml water and constantly stirred. The volume was restored to one liter and dispensed into suitable containers.

The Poisoned Food Technique for Antibiotic Sensitivity Testing for Fungi [11] was done by cultivating the test organism on a medium containing the test chemical and then measuring its growth. The treatment was incorporated and mixed well with potato dextrose agar at about 50°C and poured into culture plates using 10 ml quantities. The poisoned medium was seeded in the center with a 5-10 mm diameter agar disk of the test fungus. After the incubation duration, radical growth was measured.

2.4 Data Gathered

The number of days to microbial colonies appearance was taken by counting the number of days that the fungal contaminants appeared on the test medium. The percentage of contaminated culture media was computed by counting the contaminated culture media from the total culture divided by the total number of bottled media and multiplied by 100.

The frequency of occurrence of contaminants was determined by the number of times a contaminant appeared on the culture medium.

The technique of James and Natalie [11] was adopted for identification of the unknown isolated fungi using cotton blue in lactophenol stain. The identification was achieved by placing a drop of

the stain on clean slide with the aid of mounting needle, where a small portion of mycelium from the fungal cultures was removed and placed in a drop of lactophenol. The mycelium was spread very well on the slide with the aid of the needle. A cover slip was gently applied with little pressure to eliminate air bubbles. The slide was then mounted and observed with x10, x40 and x100 objective lenses, respectively using compound microscope. The species encountered were identified and characterized [11]. Microbial symptoms were observed based on their colony shape, colony margin/ elevation and colony color in 20 bottle test media during one month (Initial stage) observation period.

The colony of fungus was measured from edge to edge twice in the longest and shortage edge using millimeter. Data were gathered from 5th to 7th day of incubation.

The data were analyzed using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and the differences among the treatment means were compared using Honest Significant Difference (HSD) test when significant findings were obtained from ANOVA at 5% level.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Number of Days to Microbial Colonies Appearance

Microbial colonies of contaminants were observed during micro propagation of tissue-cultured abaca hybrid 7.

The bacterial and fungal contaminants in laboratories of commercial micro-propagation posed a considerable problem [11]. Moreover,

the tissue culture laboratory of the University of Southeastern Philippines also encountered both bacterial and fungal contaminants of tissue-cultured abaca hybrid 7 (*Musa textiles* Nee). Suspected *Aspergillus* sp. (Fig. 1) appeared after 10 days from initiation stage of tissue-cultured abaca. Fungi same as *Chrysosporium* sp. (Fig. 2) was observed on the 12th day and 14th day from initiation stage.

In addition tissue-cultured meriplants can become contaminated at any stage of tissue culture process [12]. Fungus may arrive with an explant, or airborne, or enter a culture [13]. The presence of workers and their levels may get high when the building is heavily populated.

3.2 Percentage of Contaminated Culture Media

Table 1 shows the percentage of contaminated media culture of tissue-cultured abaca during initial stage. It revealed that in every 20 culture media, 15 percent of fungal contaminants appeared with 10% *Chrysosporium* sp. like and 5% of these are suspected *Aspergillus* sp.

The tissue-cultured laboratory technicians of the University of Southeastern Philippines observed approximately 8.6% of fungal contaminants in tissue-cultured *Musa* spp. during initial stage.

It was reported that sub-culture process is a major source of contamination with about 5-15% of contaminants being introduced for every subculture [14]. The major cause of the microbial contamination is insufficient disinfection of explants, growth media, working tools and operators' hands.

Fig. 1. Suspected *Aspergillus* sp. (A) and *Chrysosporium* sp. (B) contaminants observed during initial stage of tissue-cultured abaca (*Musa textiles* Née) on Murashige and Skoog culture medium

Table 1. Percentage of contamination occurred in 20 culture media during initiation stage of tissue-cultured abaca (*Musa textiles* Née)

Contaminants	Number of contaminants occurred	Percentage of contaminants	Total contaminants
<i>Suspected Aspergillus</i> sp.	1	5%	15%
<i>Chrysosporium</i> sp. like	2	10%	

Despite the fact that some of these contaminants might be endogenously embedded in the plant tissues [15], some might also have emanated from contaminated tools, which were not investigated. However, mites and thrips carrying fungal spores and bacteria in and on their bodies, often gain entry through this loose fittings and travel from one vessel to another thereby contaminating the cultures. Fungal contamination of cultures is usually the first sign of a mite or thrip infestation [16]. Hence, proper sanitation and effective use of appropriate pesticides to control mites and thrips in tissue-cultured laboratories is desirable. Thorough disinfections and strict hygiene in the laboratory have achieved effective control of microbial contaminants. Movement of people within the preparatory and incubating rooms in tissue culture laboratory should be reduced significantly to avoid the spread of contaminants.

3.3 Characterization Fungal Contaminants

The principal microbial contaminants frequently reported in plant *in vitro* cultures are bacteria and

fungi [2,17]. The main fungal contaminants frequently observed in plant tissue cultures are *Alternaria tenuis* (Fr.) Keissl., *Aspergillus niger* Tiegh, *Aspergillus fumigatus* Fresenius and *Fusarium culmorum* (W.G. Smith) Sacc. [18] and [19].

The fungal contaminants of tissue-cultured abaca hybrid 7 cultures at tissue culture laboratory of University of Southeastern Philippines were identified as *Aspergillus* sp. (Table 2 and Fig. 2A) and fungal contaminant *Chrysosporium* sp. (Table 2 and Fig. 2B).

Aspergillus sp. are exogenously found in soils, water and on plant surfaces [13] but are also endophytes in some plant species and also were found in internal tissues of mallow plants. Moreover, *Aspergillus* spp. is one of the major contaminant in tissue-culture of *Lilium candidum* L., *Vigna* sp., *Musa* sp., *Manihot* sp., and *Hibiscus* sp. [20].

Chrysosporium sp. is a keratinophilic filamentous fungus commonly isolated from soil where it lives on remains of hairs and feathers.

Table 2. Characterization and identification of fungal contaminants of tissue-cultured abaca hybrid 7 (*Musa textiles* Née)

Contaminants	Cultural characteristics	Morphological characteristics
<i>Aspergillus</i> sp.	Colonies are flat, circle, filamentous, velvety, woolly or cottony texture. Colony color is gray to green at center with a white border. The reverse is yellow to pale yellow.	Conidiophores bear heads, long and hyaline that terminates in bulbous heads while conidia are globose to sub-globose and usually yellowish green and dark brown.
<i>Chrysosporium</i> sp.	Colonies are semi-elevated, circle, and fairly rapid grower and smooth. Colony color is white to off-white. The reverse is white to off-white color.	Produce septate, hyaline hyphae. Conidia are more often formed at the ends of simple or branched conidiophores of varying lengths. Conidiophores were ramified, forming tree-like structures. Remnants of the attaching structure may, for a time, remained attached. Conidial walls were thin-walled and the exterior was usually smooth [11].

Fig. 2. Photomicrograph of *Aspergillus* sp. (A) and of *Chrysosporium* sp. (B) of tissue-cultured abaca (*Musa textiles* Née)

Chrysosporium sp. is occasionally isolated from nail scrapings, skin, especially from feet, and may cause skin infections and onychomycosis in humans, but because they are common soil saprophytes they are usually considered as contaminants. They are also occasional contaminants of respiratory samples. Furthermore, fungal contaminants are associated in human skin and can be transmitted during micropropagation process [20].

Microbes are living biological contaminants that can be transmitted by infected people, animals and indoor air, and they can also travel through the air and get inside homes and buildings. The occurrence of exogenous fungal in abaca (*Musa textiles* Née) *in vitro* cultures in this study was possibly due to an inadequate surface disinfection. Several studies have also associated the incidence of exogenous fungal contaminants in plant *in vitro* cultures with an insufficient disinfection [2,21]. Therefore, contamination was possibly due to insufficient aseptic places among workers during tissue culture operations.

3.4 Colony Diameter of *Aspergillus* spp.

The colony diameter of *Aspergillus* sp. as affected by different antibiotics at 3rd, 4th, 5th, 6th, and 7th days of incubation is shown in Table 3 and Figs. 3-4. Analysis of variance showed significant differences among treatment means.

At three days of incubation, it was observed that the growth of *Aspergillus* sp. was significantly inhibited by Treatment 5 (Benomyl, 100 mg·L⁻¹) with an average mean of 10.46 mm colony diameter. This was followed by Treatment 4

(Streptomycin, 200 mg·L⁻¹ + Nystatin 1 ml·L⁻¹) with an average mean of 13.92 mm and followed by Treatment 3 (Nystatin 1 ml·L⁻¹) with an average mean of 17.17 mm. Highest growths were observed in Treatment 2 (Streptomycin 200 mg·L⁻¹) and Treatment 1 (Control) with 23.33mm and 24.20 mm, respectively.

At four to six days of incubation, it was observed that the growth was significantly decreased by Treatment 5 (Benomyl 100 mg·L⁻¹) application with average fungal colony diameter means of 10.92 mm, 13.08 mm and 19.67 mm, respectively. This was followed by Treatment 4 (Streptomycin, 200 mg·L⁻¹ + Nystatin 1 ml·L⁻¹) and Treatment 3 (Nystatin 1 ml·L⁻¹) with average means ranging from 16.83 mm to 34.25mm, respectively. While the lowest inhibition was observed at Treatment 1 (No Treatment) and Treatment 2 (Streptomycin 200 mg·L⁻¹) with average means ranging from 29.42 mm to 48.17 mm, respectively.

At seven days of incubation, it was observed that the growth of *Aspergillus* sp. was significantly inhibited by Treatment 5 (Benomyl 100 mg·L⁻¹) application with an average mean of 33.92 mm. This followed by Treatment 4 (Streptomycin 200 mg·g⁻¹ + Nystatin 1 ml·L⁻¹) with an average mean of 37.50 mm and was followed by Treatment 3 (Nystatin 1 ml·L⁻¹) with an average mean of 40.58 mm. Highest growths were observed in Treatment 2 (Streptomycin, 200 mg·L⁻¹) and Treatment 1 (Control) with 65.75 mm and 68.25 mm, respectively.

The growth increments of *Aspergillus* sp. were also highest in Treatment 1 (Control) and Treatment 2 (Streptomycin, 200 mg·L⁻¹) at 3rd to

Fig. 3. The inhibitory effect exhibited by different levels of antibiotics on *Aspergillus* sp. fungal contaminant of tissue-cultured abaca (*Musa textiles* Née) after 5 days of incubation (90 mm scale)

7th day of incubation. Lowest growth increments of *Aspergillus* sp. were observed in Treatment 5 (Benomyl 100 mg·L⁻¹) on the 4th to 5th day of incubation while Treatment 4 (Streptomycin 200 mg·L⁻¹ + Nystatin 1 ml·L⁻¹) on the 6th to 7th day of incubation.

The most effective chemotherapeutic substance to control the growth of fungi contaminants of tissue-cultured *Lilium candidum* L. is achieved by utilizing Benomyl (100 mg dm⁻³) + Nystatin (100 mg dm⁻³) treatment combination [22]. Moreover, Benomyl at 0.25 to 0.40 µg·ml⁻¹ induced reverse

mutations from both biotin and pyridoxine requirement in the excision-deficient UT517 strain of *Aspergillus nidulans* (Eidam) G. Winter [21]. Reverse mutations from adenine requirement in a UV-sensitive strain (UT540) of *Aspergillus nidulans* were also induced. The fungicide Benomyl was evaluated for effectiveness in controlling *Aspergillus nidulans* and *Ascomycete* sp. fungal contaminants, as well as their impact on the growth and development of *Arabidopsis* seedlings. Benomyl proved to be an effective inhibitor of all *Aspergillus nidulans* and *Ascomycete* sp. contaminants in

Fig. 4. The inhibitory effect exhibited by different levels of antibiotics on *Aspergillus* sp. fungal contaminant of tissue-cultured abaca (*Musa textiles* Née) taken after 7 days of incubation (90 mm scale)

concentrations as low as 2 ppm within the agar medium, and no evidence of phytotoxicity was observed until concentrations exceeded 20 ppm [21].

3.5 Colony Diameter (mm) of *Chrysosporium* sp. Like Fungus

The colony diameter of *Chrysosporium* sp. like fungus as affected by different antibiotics at 3rd, 4th, 5th, 6th, and 7th days of incubation is shown in Table 4 and Figs. 5-6. Analysis of variance showed significant differences among treatment

means. The different antibiotics were applied using food poison technique.

At three to seventh days of incubation, it was observed that the growth of *Chrysosporium* sp. was significantly inhibited by Treatment 3 (Nystatin, 1 ml·L⁻¹) and Treatment 4 (Streptomycin, 200 mg·L⁻¹ + Nystatin, 1 ml·L⁻¹) with an average colony diameter means ranging from 10.08 mm to 30.17 mm, respectively. This was followed by Treatment 5 (Benomyl, 100 mg·L⁻¹) with the means of 15.92 mm and 44.42 mm. Highest growths were

observed in Treatment 2 (Streptomycin, 200 mg·L⁻¹) and Treatment 1 (Control) with average means of 22.58 mm to 63.42 mm. The same trend was also observed in terms of growth increments at third to seventh days of incubation. It was observed that fungi subjected to Treatment 3 (Nystatin, 1 ml·L⁻¹) had the lowest growth increase, followed by Treatment 4 (Streptomycin, 200 mg·L⁻¹ + Nystatin, 1 ml·L⁻¹) and Treatment 5 (Benomyl, 100 mg·L⁻¹) while fungi on control media (Treatment 1) and Treatment 5 (Benomyl, 100 mg·L⁻¹) had the highest growth increase.

Nystatin binds to ergosterol in fungal membrane causing membrane to become leaky and causing fungal growth inhibition [23].

Among the antibiotic treatments, Nystatin is the most effective. Furthermore, Nystatin concentration will allow the growth of fungus during the first 48 hours and during equal period of incubation, while Nystatin at 200 unit/ml prevented the germination of spores and growth of *Apergillus* spp. [23]. The spores of *A. fumigatus* (at the concentration used) were killed by 6000 units of Nystatin/ml, but not until they had been exposed for longer than 4 hours.

Fig. 5. The inhibitory effect exhibited by different levels of antibiotics on the fungal contaminants same as *Chrysosporium* spp. on tissue-cultured abaca (*Musa textiles* Néé) after 5 days of incubation

Fig. 6. The inhibitory effect exhibited by different levels of antibiotics on the fungal contaminants same as *Chrysosporium* spp. on tissue-cultured abaca (*Musa textiles* Née) after 7 days of incubation (90 mm scale)

Table 3. Zone of growth (mm) of *Aspergillus* sp. of tissue-cultured abaca (*Musa textiles* Née) as affected by different antibiotics after 3 to 7 days of incubation

Treatments	3 rd day old	4 th day old	5 th day old	6 th day old	7 th day old
T1- Control (No treatment)	23.33 ^c	29.50 ^c	41.25 ^c	45.25 ^c	65.75 ^c
T2- Streptomycin (200 mg·L ⁻¹)	24.28 ^c	29.67 ^c	42.50 ^c	48.17 ^c	68.25 ^c
T3- Nystatin (1 ml·L ⁻¹)	17.17 ^b	20.17 ^b	29.50 ^b	34.25 ^b	40.58 ^b
T4- Streptomycin (200 mg·L ⁻¹) + Nystatin (1 ml·L ⁻¹)	13.92 ^{ab}	16.83 ^b	26.25 ^b	30.67 ^b	37.33 ^{ab}
T5- Benomyl (Chemical check) (100 mg·L ⁻¹)	10.46 ^a	10.92 ^a	13.08 ^a	19.67 ^a	33.92 ^a
C.V. %	9.86%	8.10%	5.78%	5.52%	4.77%

Table 4. Zone of growth (mm) of *Chrysosporium* sp. like on tissue-cultured abaca (*Musa textiles* Née) as affected by different antibiotics after 3 to 7 days of incubation

Treatments	3 rd day old	4 th day old	5 th day old	6 th day old	7 th day old
T1- Control (No treatment)	22.58 ^c	27.92 ^c	38.83 ^d	46.08 ^d	60.00 ^d
T2- Streptomycin (200 mg·L ⁻¹)	24.92 ^c	29.58 ^c	40.67 ^d	46.75 ^d	63.42 ^d
T3- Nystatin (1 ml·L ⁻¹)	10.08 ^a	10.83 ^a	14.17 ^a	14.58 ^a	16.58 ^a
T4- Streptomycin (200 mg·L ⁻¹) + Nystatin (1 ml·L ⁻¹)	11.67 ^a	15.83 ^a	22.83 ^b	27.50 ^b	30.17 ^b
T5- Benomyl (Chemical check) (100 mg·L ⁻¹)	15.92 ^b	22.25 ^b	31.17 ^c	36.83 ^c	44.42 ^c
C.V. %	8.60%	8.98%	5.30%	4.92%	5.81%

Benomyl (100 g cm⁻³) reduced the contamination of cherry. Moreover, Benomyl is used as a pre-harvest systemic fungicide, and as a post-harvest dip or dust [24]. It combats a wide range of fungal diseases. In this study, it is less effective than Nystatin.

4. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Suspected *Aspergillus* sp. appeared after 10 days from initiation stage of tissue-cultured abaca while fungi like *Chrysosporium* sp. were observed on the 12th and 14th day from initiation stage. It revealed that in every 20 culture media, 15 percent of fungal contaminants appeared with 10% *Chrysosporium* sp. like and 5% of these are suspected *Aspergillus* sp.

Further tests showed that T5 - Benomyl (Chemical check) 100 mg·L⁻¹) significantly inhibited the growth of *Aspergillus* sp. While, T3 - Nystatin (1 ml·L⁻¹) restrained the growth of fungal contaminants like *Chrysosporium* sp. These fungal species cause death of the culture material from some probable sources of contaminations such as handling of plant materials, culture vessels and laboratory sanitation.

The result of the study suggests that both Benomyl (Chemical check - 100 mg·L⁻¹) and Nystatin (1 ml·L⁻¹) can be used to inhibit growth of fungal contaminants such as *Aspergillus* sp. and *Chrysosporium* sp. Both Benomyl and Nystatin can be used in the tissue culture laboratory to verify results and test the toxicity of the chemicals to the tissue-cultured abaca meristem.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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